

Reading and writing the world with mathematics: Exploring possibilities with socially vulnerable Brazilian students

Luana Pedrita Fernandes de Oliveira, São Paulo State University (UNESP),

✉ oli.luanapf@gmail.com

This article presents a doctoral research project related to reading and writing the world with mathematics from a Critical Mathematics Education perspective. From a qualitative approach, the research aims to identify potentials landscapes for investigation so that students can read and write the world with mathematics, through generative themes based on Paulo Freire's theory. As methodological procedures, it's intended to produce field reports, interviews, and alternative resources and it's expected that great possibilities and potential scenarios for reading and writing the world with mathematics within the school will emerge.

The research project and the theoretical framework

The topic of interest is Teaching and Learning Mathematics for Social Justice, in the settings of a Brazilian public school, with the aim of identifying possibilities and potential for students, promoting reading and writing the world with mathematics from generative themes.

The main theorists who have supported this research so far are Eric Gutstein, Ole Skovsmose and Paulo Freire. These authors stated education must be intrinsically motivated by concerns related to social, democratic, economic, cultural and political issues, aiming the transformation of society through education for social justice.

Paulo Freire, probably the most important reference in critical education in Brazil, who developed part of his work in non-formal educational environments, introduces concerns and manifestations about the relations of power and social, political and economic inequality. According to Freire (2001), education is a political act and an act of knowledge, centered on the dialogic act. Freire stresses the importance of the subject learning to read the world, understanding the text and the context, saying his word.

The reading of the world precedes the reading of the word, hence the subsequent reading of the word cannot do without the continuity of reading the word. Language and reality are dynamically linked (Freire, 2001, p. 11).

When a person learns to read the world and, consequently, to say his words, with the language and reality involved, he/she starts to reinterpret his own reality, while he/she learns

Please cite as: Oliveira, L. P. F. (2021). Reading and writing the world with mathematics: Exploring possibilities with socially vulnerable Brazilian students. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 215–218). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5392624>

to understand themselves in the world. The person is placed in the world as a person of a historic struggle against oppressions and inequalities.

Ole Skovsmose argues that mathematics education is not neutral, that it is necessary to be concerned about the interests behind the subjects, to question what or for whom it serves, what are the knowledge-forming interests that are connected to the content (Skovsmose, 2001). In this sense, Skovsmose (2010) emphasizes that the critical approach needs to rely more on uncertainties, than certainties and ready answers, considering that “any approach that can be characterized as critical is left open. And, with such uncertainty, a critical approach can be built” (Skovsmose, 2010, p. 13).

For Gutstein, a mathematical educator, reading and writing the world with mathematics is to investigate and criticize structures and situations of oppression that are present in everyday life, especially those that involve social injustices, such as racism, feminicide, social inequality, etc. It also highlights this action for education, so that students learn mathematics and, at the same time, use it to study their social reality, in the search for understandings and transformations of this world (Gutstein, 2016a). Gutstein believes that teaching mathematics for social justice is synonymous of reading and writing the world with mathematics or teaching critical mathematics, stating that Ole Skovsmose and Paulo Freire have a wide influence on his thoughts, practices and research.

It is necessary to highlight that those three authors, mentioned above, assume in their understandings the dialogue as the main element so that an education for social justice occurs. Understanding dialogue in the same sense Faustino (2018), as the encounter of different world views that build new world views.

In this perspective of dialogue, Skovsmose (2010) brings the notion of *landscape of investigation*, which seeks the active participation of students in the teaching and learning process, inviting teachers and students to dialogue and walk through different learning environments. According to the author, “landscape of investigation opens up new possibilities for reflection. And the notion of reflection is important for any type of critical mathematical education” (Skovsmose, 2010, p. 13).

It is in this literature that seek to expand the understanding of critical mathematical education and social justice, within the school environment, in which the research project is being built.

The context of research project and methods

The research will be carried out in a public school located on the suburbs of a city of the State of São Paulo, in Brazil, in a context of social vulnerability in basic sanitation, food, work, income, rights, affectivity, etc.

Based on this context, this project intends to list and negotiating with students, through dialogue, some possible themes of interest to them, which will become generative themes, from Paulo Freire’s perspective. It is expected that themes related to the context of the school and its surroundings will emerge, with social dimensions, and from that start a reflective dialogue of students with the researcher teacher for reading and writing the world with

mathematics will begin. more details about the methodology and methodological procedures will be further defined, because the author is only in the first semester of the doctorate and the project is still in the initial phase.

In the book *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, Paulo Freire brought generative themes as a teaching methodology in the context of literacy for peasants. Generative themes are concrete representations of the ideas, hopes, doubts, outlooks, fears, values, and challenges that arise from the thought-language of men and women in their relationship with the world (Freire, 2011). Noting “that the generative theme is not found in men isolated from reality, nor in reality separate from men. It can only be understood in human-world relations” (Freire, 2011, p. 136).

It is noticeable that he did not address ideas of mathematics in his work, but Gutstein (2016a; 2016b) makes this connection between Paulo Freire’s ideas and mathematics, bringing the concepts of reading and writing the world with mathematics. Gutstein (2016b) developed a work focused on mathematics education, that involved

collaboration with students to discover their generative themes; creation of tasks based on these themes, so that students learn mathematics, at the same time that they prepare to read the world (Gutstein, 2016b, p. 462).

In this direction, in the research project, it is intended to use this methodology of generative themes in the context of mathematics, in a reality of periphery and social vulnerability in Brazil.

In the State of São Paulo, in Brazil, there is the Integral Education Program (PEI) for public schools, in which students spend most of their day at school. This program was created in 2012 for middle and high school and, since then, the number of schools that adhere to this proposal has been increasing. The author of this article teaches at one of these public schools, which is part of the PEI, and will conduct her research at her school, researching his own practice. The research will be developed with a group of students in an elective subject.

The elective subject was chosen for develop the research, since in this space the teacher is expected to promote the enrichment, expansion and diversification of the contents and themes. According to the Integral Education Program Guidelines (São Paulo, 2014), “elective subject occupies a central place with regard to the diversification of school experiences, offering a privileged space for experiment, interdisciplinary and further studies” (p. 29).

Thus, in the elective subject it is possible to work with mathematics covering different contexts, exploring interdisciplinary freely. Therefore, this project will not be developed in the mathematics subject which would have a limited space for the development of the proposal, due to the skills and programmatic content of the curriculum.

The elective subject also has a differential, which are the students who choose which elective they want to take in the semester. All teachers at the school offer subjects, disseminating the proposals, and students choose one that is close to their interest.

Considering the synergy of the ideas that have been explained so far, the reflections converge to the following guiding question: When working with generative themes in an

elective subject, what are the potentials landscape of investigation for reading and writing the world with mathematics?

It is expected that potential landscapes of investigation for reading and writing in the world with mathematics for social justice will emerge, in the context of public school.

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